

EXPRESSION OF EDUCATION AND UPBRINGING ISSUES IN WESTERN PEDAGOGY

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Abstract. *This article reveals the ideas of Western scholars in their creative work, their views on education, the methods of upbringing instilling them in the minds of the younger generation, their correct use in life, and important aspects of the teacher's skills in the process of pedagogical education.*

Keywords: *pedagogue, consciousness, idea, upbringing, education, morality, perfect person, humanity, spiritual qualities, national values, national thinking.*

ВЫРАЖЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ И ВОСПИТАНИЯ В ЗАПАДНОЙ ПЕДАГОГИКЕ

Аннотация. *В статье раскрываются идеи западных ученых в их творчестве, их взгляды на образование, методы воспитания, внедряемые ими в сознание подрастающего поколения, их правильное использование в жизни, а также важные аспекты мастерства учителя в процессе педагогического образования.*

Ключевые слова: *педагог, сознание, идея, воспитание, образование, нравственность, совершенный человек, гуманность, духовные качества, национальные ценности, национальное мышление.*

In recent years, our President has paid special attention to the education of our children and youth: "Currently, the education of youth remains an issue that will never lose its relevance and importance for us. Today's rapidly changing world is opening up new opportunities for humanity and young people. At the same time, it also exposes them to various evil dangers that have never been seen before. Malicious forces are turning naive, cave children against their parents and their country, endangering their lives and livelihoods. In such tense and dangerous circumstances, we, parents, teachers, the public, and the community, must further increase our vigilance and awareness on this issue. "We should raise our children ourselves, not leave them in the hands of others,"¹ - he emphasizes. It also emphasizes that, given the globalization situation, reforms in the field of education cannot be delayed. The needs of socio-economic development, which have led to a change in the priorities and target areas of education, are confronting higher pedagogical schools

¹ Мирзиёев Ш.М. Қонун устуворлиги ва инсон манфаатларини таъминлаш – юрт тараққиёти ва халқ фаровонлигининг гарови. – Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2017. – Б. 22-23.

with the need to educate a new generation of teachers who not only have practical skills, but also require tools for transformation, as well as mental activity that allows them to see the development strategies of each child. The demand for a teacher who seeks and is able to see general, natural cause-and-effect relationships behind individual, specific pedagogical situations predetermines the effectiveness of one or another method of achieving educational goals, and provides the direction of the future teacher training plan. These processes are aimed at developing the teacher's theoretical and pedagogical thinking.²

According to the tradition formed in the philosophy of ancient antiquity, the main characteristic that distinguishes a person from other creatures is his thinking (Democritus, Plato, Aristotle). Man is, first of all, the mind. Based on this idea of Aristotle, it can be said that thinking is the main characteristic of a person.

Based on this, ancient thinkers highly valued the role of thought in human life. "The happiness of people does not lie in slaves or money, but in prudence and right thinking,"³ Democritus emphasized. According to the concept he created, thinking is of great importance in human life and activity as a factor that limits human desires and regulates human behavior. S.L. Rubinstein sees the importance of thinking in behavior in the saturation of the latter with variability, as a result of which conditions arise for controlling actions by highlighting its important aspects, connections and relationships in accordance with the changing components of the external situation.⁴

The implementation of the above requires the subject to be included in a certain part of reality and establish relationships within the framework of a certain activity. For a teacher, this aspect is professional pedagogical activity in the field of education, the specific features of which determine the characteristics of the subject (teacher) in reflecting the surrounding reality. In this sense, pedagogical thinking is a professional characteristic that "shapes" the teacher, on the one hand, allows him to be a professional, and on the other hand, distinguishes him from representatives of other professions. In addition, under the influence of pedagogical thinking, a strategy of behavior is developed in accordance with the characteristics of the situation, the principles and norms of individual consciousness, which corresponds to the real needs of practice, and plays a regulatory role in the teacher's activities. From the point of view of the relationship between behavior and thinking, the concept put forward by A.N. Leontiev is noteworthy.

According to him, there is an analogy between the relationship between a person and the world and his inner life under the influence of the structure of external activity (which constitutes

² G.Xolmirzayeva. G'arb mutafakkirlari qarashlari pedagogik tafakkurni shakllantirishning nazariy asoslaridan biri sifatida. Konferensiya materiallari to'plami. 2024. 201-204-b

³ Андреева Н.Н. Философия и история образования. - Москва, 1999.

⁴ Рубинштейн С.Л. Основы общей психологии. - СПб., 2002.

behavior) and internal activity (which constitutes thinking). Internal thinking activity is not only created through external practice, but also has the same structural structure as it.⁵

Along with medieval encyclopedists, the Czech scientist Jan Amos Comenius, the Swiss educator Johann Heinrich Pestalozzi, the German educator Adolf Disterweg, and the Russian educator K.D. Ushinsky made a great contribution to the creation of the methodology of pedagogical science. Nowadays, the concept of a well-rounded person has become associated with the concepts of building a civil society and being a selfless child for the Motherland. We now need to form and educate not only individual mature individuals, but also a well-rounded generation.

Only then will we have a society of well-rounded generations, individuals with intellectual potential.

In ancient Greece, Socrates, Pythagoras, Aristotle, and Plato created the philosophical basis of their ideas on human development and upbringing. Aristotle, in his "Advice to Alexander" (he was the teacher of Alexander the Great, and Alexander, in turn, preferred Aristotle to his father), emphasized that the highest virtue of a person is piety, faith, and knowledge, that is, he said: "Piety is perfected through faith. Faith is formed under the shadow of thought and thought."⁶

In short, it studies and analyzes the pedagogy created by the peoples of the East and the West, based on folk oral creativity, and the progressive ideas of thinkers, enlighteners, educators, and scientists on education, and identifies the laws, rules, and necessary qualities for the formation of a well-rounded personality.

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⁵ Леонтьев А.Н. Избранные психологические произведения: В 2-х т. Т.2.- Москва,1983.

⁶ J.Hasanboyev va boshqalar. Pedagogika. "Noshir". Toshkent. 2016. 25-b

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